

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B272
Date: 26 February 2007
Take Off 08:54:54
Landing: 14:23:35
Flight Time 5h28m41

Campaign: GFDEX – Mesoscale Cyclone and Targeted observations of SAP south of Iceland (Plan 44)

Operating Area: South of Iceland (Targ Obs)

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	DFL
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay Rae	DFL
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	DFL
4	Mission Scientist 1	Ian Renfrew	University of Toronto
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry / AVAPS / CCM2	Bob Wells	FAAM
7	Mission Scientist 2	Nina Petersen	UEA
8	Mission Scientist 3	Emma Irvine	Reading University
9	Mission Scientist 4	Dave Sproson	UEA
10	Mission Scientist 5	Inge Johansson	University of Bergen, Norway
11	Mission Scientist 6	Haraldur Olafsson	University of Iceland, Iceland
12			
13			
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15			
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17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B272 Track 26-FEB-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b272
 Date: 26/2/07
 Project: GFDEX
 Location: SE of Iceland

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
065640		Start-Up	0.00 kft	078	63'59.66N, 22'37.66W
084444		inu to nav	0.06 kft	078	
084540		engine start	0.06 kft	078	
085024		taxy	0.06 kft	094	
085454		T/O	0.08 kft	179	from Keflavik
090448		jw/nevz	17.2 kft	140	zero
092229	095834	Run 1	25.0 kft	147	
092229		Sonde 1			
092747		Sonde 2	25.0 kft	070	
093246		Sonde 3	25.0 kft	084	
093801		Sonde 4	25.0 kft	085	
094310		Sonde 5	25.0 kft	085	
094851		Sonde 6	25.0 kft	087	
095342		Sonde 7	25.0 kft	088	
095834		Sonde 8			
102142		Sonde 9	25.0 kft	194	
105155		Sonde 10	26.0 kft	281	
110203		jw/nevz	26.0 kft	346	zero
111207		Sonde 11	27.0 kft	345	
113030		Sonde 12	27.0 kft	348	
114705		Sonde 13	27.0 kft	338	
115847	121515	Profile 1	26.6 kft	194	rate of dec 200fpm
120013	121515	Profile 1	24.2 - 2.2 kft	194	
120128		Profile 1	21.3 kft	195	rod 3000ft/min
120149		Profile 1	20.2 kft	191	
120441		Profile 1	14.3 kft	101	1500ft/min
120659		Profile 1	11.5 kft	235	1000ft/min
121403		jw/nevz	3.5 kft	211	zero
121516	125048	Run 2	2.2 - 2.0 kft	227	
131956		Sonde 14	28.0 kft	259	
142335		Land	0.09 kft	002	at Keflavik

B272 Track 26-FEB-07

GFDex Sortie Brief – B272 – 26 February 2007

Mesoscale Cyclone and Targeted observations of SAP south of Iceland (Plan 44)

Mission Scientists: Ian Renfrew, Nina Petersen, Emma Irvine, Inge Johansson, Haraldur Olafsson, Dave Sproson

Aims

- Map out 3D structure of mesoscale cyclone using a mixture of high-level and low-level legs
- High-level legs at 25-27 kft, straight and level, cutting through cyclone with cross.
- Low-level legs at 2000 ft and 5000 ft, straight and level, to sample wind, temperature, etc
- Dropsonde sampling every 30 nm (30-50 km) within cyclone
- Dropsonde release near Icelandic coast for topographic gravity waves
- Dropsonde releases evenly spaced around SAP for Targeted observation purposes

GFD44	Time	Manoeuvre	Distance (nm)	Duration (min)	Total time (min)
1	0900	Take off Keflavík , transit to 62.5N, 21W.	100	~20	~20
2		Straight level run at 25-30 kft, due east to 62.5N, 13W. Most efficient speed. Dropsonde releases every 30 nm (7 in total)	221	~45	~65
3		High-level leg due south (heading 180°) to 60.5N, 13W. Dropsonde release here.	120	~25	~90
4		High-level leg due west (heading 270°) to 60.5N, 17W. Dropsonde release here.	118	~25	~115
5		Straight level run at 25-30 kft, due north to 64.5N, 17W. From 61.5 N to 63.5N, Dropsonde releases every 30 nm (4 in total).	240	~50	~165
6		High-level leg from 64.5N, 17W to 64.33N, 16W. Dropsonde release here	28	~6	~170
7		Profile descent to 63.5N, 17W. Fast descent (2000 ft per min?) to 10 kft. Slower descent (1000 ft per min) to 2000 ft.	56	~20	~190
8		Straight low-level leg at 2000 ft to 61N, 17W (heading due south). Science speed	150	~45	~235
9		Climb and turn to head due north to 62.5N, 17W at 5000 ft	90	~20	~255
10		Climb and head to 60.5N, 21W. Dropsonde release here	165	~30	~285
11		Transit to Keflavik	215	~35	~320

Mesoscale cyclone - GFDex Plan 44

- outbound
- high-level
- low-level
- return
- dropsonde leg

Mission Scientists Debriefing Sheet

Flight No. **B272**

Mesoscale Cyclone and Targeted observations of SAP south of Iceland (Plan 44)

Date: **26 February 2007**

Aims

- Map out 3D structure of mesoscale cyclone using a mixture of high-level and low-level legs
- High-level legs at 25-27 kft, straight and level, cutting through cyclone with cross.
- Low-level legs at 2000 ft and 5000 ft, straight and level, to sample wind, temperature, etc
- Dropsonde sampling every 30 nm (30-50 km) within cyclone
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Assessment of the Flight

Generally successful, with some dropsonde problems.

14 Dropsondes were released, with a higher density of sondes released in area of weak mesoscale cyclone. Two dropsondes did not generate a launch code and so could NOT be sent to the GTS. These were drop numbers 7 and 12 (unfortunately failure of 12 affected targeted observation component of mission). Drop 3 did not have any data till 800 mb. All dropsondes that could be transmitted onto the GTS in real time, made the Met Office database in time for the 12 UTC forecast, i.e. made the QG cycle.

Dropsonde cross-sections did not fully capture the weak mesocyclone – it had moved out of the area that we had notam's to drop into. However there was some signature.

Low-level (2000 ft) leg did capture flow reversal associated with mesoscale cyclone, towards end of this leg. Hence this leg was extended (in flight) to fully capture the cyclone. Some interesting cloud physics. Cloud base around 2000 to 1500 feet.

Summary of weather conditions

Generally easterly flow.

Convective and stratus cloud associated with weak mesoscale cyclone. Clear air immediately in the wake of Iceland.

Ian Renfrew

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.272**... Date **26 Feb 07**... Name **Ian Renfrew**... Page **1** of **2**...

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
08:55	1			Keflavik	Take off
9.22	2	25 kft	90	62N 19W	Drop 1 - 9:33 landed: cloud RH large at 850mb 6 mi ⁻¹ , 50 deg
9.25	2	"	"		Above ^{cloud} cloud deck, some convective clouds ahead.
	2	"	"	62N 17W	
9.28	2	"	"	62N 17°42'	Drop 2 - RH ↑ 820mb 7 m/s 60 deg
9.32	2	"	"	62N 16°36'	Drop 3 - no data till 800mb 11 mi ⁻¹ 60 deg
9.37	2	"	"	62N 15°36'	Drop 4 - RH ↑ 800mb 14 mi ⁻¹ 60 deg, 10 m/s 70 deg
9.43	2	"	"	62N 14°24'	Drop 5 - RH ↑ 750mb 9 m/s 50 deg
9.48	2	"	"	62N	Drop 6 - RH ↑ 550mb 7 mi ⁻¹ , shear to 110 deg at 900
9.53	2	"	"	62N 12°W	Drop 7 - No launch parameter. → No GTS *
9.58	2	"	"	62N 11°W	Drop 8 - RH ↑ 550mb 3 mi ⁻¹ 310 deg
9.58	3	"	180	"	End of Run
10.21	3	"	180	60N 11W	Drop 9 - RH, 2 weeks maxima, no cell detected cloud top. 3 m/s 150°, shear to 5 m/s, 250 at 900
10.51	4	26 kft	270	60N 14°22'W	Drop 10 - RH, 2 maxima at 850 & 700 6 mi ⁻¹ 180°
11.12	5	27 kft	0	61.5N 15W	Climb
11.12	5	"	0	61.5 15W	Drop 11 - RH 800mb, cloud deck lower and 270° 9 mi ⁻¹ 40°, shear to 2 m/s at 900mb
11.22	5	"	0	62° 12' 15W	Clouds clearing below. Next drop into clear air
11.30	5	"	0	63° 15W	Drop 12 - No launch parameter → No GTS *
11.30	6	"	329	"	Turn.
11.47	6	"	"	61° 12' 61° 12' 16W	Drop 13 - RH 40% or lower, some T perturbation Many waves in WS & WB
11.47	7	"	"	"	Turn & slow descent
11.58	7	Descent	"	63°	Profile descent
11.59	7	24 kft	"	63°36' 15W	2000 ft per min, 3000 ft per min

936
938

9.50?
near road

2

800
mb

Mission Scientist's Log

Emma

Flight No **B272** Date 26.02.07 Name GNP Page 1 of 3

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
08.55					Take off
		#2			8 drops. release not 7!
09.25					DS1
09:22	1	25kft	147	62°0N 18°54W	Dropsonde 1 released
09:22	#	25kft	147		p = 375mb, v = 324kts Cumulus
09:27	1	25kft	70	61°54N 14°48W	Dropsonde 2 (appear as #3)
					p = 375mb v = 334kts cumulus
09:33	1	25kft	70	62°N 16°30W	Dropsonde 3
					p = 375mb v = 325kts shallow cumulus to left deeper to right
09:38	1	25kft	84	62°N 15°30W	Dropsonde 4
					p = 375mb v = 310kts currus layer on top, some icing in larger convective clouds
09:43	#	25kft	85	62°N 14°24W	Dropsonde 5
					p = 375mb v = 319kts
09:49	#	25kft	85	62°N 13°6W	Dropsonde 6
					p = 375mb v = 326kts more stratocum on left, cloud amount increasing to S.
09:54	+	25kft	87	62°N 12°W	Dropsonde 7
					p = 375mb v = 324kts currus shield evident to SE, top ~18-20kft cloud height increasing.
09:59	#	25kft	88	61°54N 62°N 11°W	Dropsonde 8
					p = 375mb v = 327kts
10.22		25kft	145	60°24N 11°0 W	DS9. Clear underneath
					p = 375 hPa v = 307kt.
10.52		26kft	280	60°0N 14°42' W	DS10
					p = 359 hPa v = 329kt.

NE
10:45
1047
FAIL
no bar
line
10:4

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.272** Date 26.02.07 Name GNP Page ? of 3

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:52					Clouds again ^{stratified w/ cumu}
					First 4 DS successfully send 10:37 / 10:41 / 10:44 / 10:49 5th: 10:54 / 10:57 / 11:00 / 11:11 / 11:31 / 12:01
10:58					strong winds 55 m/s 305°
11:01					Comm. starting again. more wind 43 m/s 299°
					Captain feels jet further east than exp
11:04					wind dropping 38 m/s 302° Steels of cumulus
11:12		2680ft	345	61°24'N 64°54'W	DS 11 p = 343 hPa. v = 344 kt.
11:17					the temp. has fallen by ~10°C in 5 min
11:22					Clouds breaking up.
11:31		2700ft	350	63°00'N 15°W	DS 12 <u>FAILED?</u> no launch line p = 344 hPa v = 341 kt.
11:47		2700ft	343	64°12'N 16°54'W	DS 13 p = 344 hPa v = 341 kt.
					few clouds. fantastic view over jetcell ^{water-}
12:00		2200ft			spec. hum starts to be no 2g ^{12g}
12:15		2200ft			q = 2 g kg ⁻¹ clear skies ^{12g}
12:26		2000ft			wind 11 m/s cloud base ^{in front} w/ PL 030
12:27					just crossing 62N, going underneath the cloud ^{total water > 0}
12:32					12 m/s 70° q = 3.11 g kg ⁻¹
					⇒ incr. from 8 m/s at start in ^{no change} wind dir.

7
1239

out of cloud.
 total water in cloud up to 0.34 g m^{-3}
 flying at cloud tops 2000ft.
 and then lower.

1242

Wind changed from 270°
 to 300°

Inc. in Θ from 276-278
 from 1239-1242

1246

Θ fell by 3 degs. when
 going into the cloud?

13:20

Heading = 259 v = 354 kts
 Height = 24 kft, p = 388 hPa.

60°N 49°W DS14
 180541

1340: Synoptic data bank

14.25 (roughly) landing

FAAM Dropsonde Flight Log

Flight No.	B272	Date	26/02/2007
Page No.	of	Operator	BW

GMT	Sonde No.	Event	Comments
		<i>e.g. launch, splashdown</i>	<i>e.g. wind data? PTH data? Lat/Long NB strings of dropsonde data contain: time, pressure hPa, T deg C, RH %, wind direction deg, wind speed m/s, longitude, latitude, height m</i>
092230	1	Launch	376.10 -41.90 41.88 282.70 39.90 - 15.60 -18.987600 62.001800 7618.80
093139	1	Splashdown	1012.23 3.43 62.59 32.62 6.18 - 10.80 -18.888211 61.970373 332.94
	2	Not launched	No PCU detected on initialisation
	2		
092748	3	Launch	369.41 4.86 999.00 999.00 999.00 99.00 999.000000 99.000000 99999.00
093627	3	Splashdown	1012.45 3.38 66.11 52.34 6.08 - 11.40 -17.751281 61.957728 99999.00
093248	4	Launch	373.05 -9.62 1.91 269.80 95.47 0.00 -16.725608 62.047427 8042.54
093926	4	Splashdown	1011.60 1.87 79.40 999.00 999.00 99.00 999.000000 99.000000 359.63
093803	5	Launch	375.60 -44.30 14.22 292.80 33.30 - 16.20 -15.588500 62.057000 7626.40
094659	5	Splashdown	1011.65 2.47 72.09 999.00 999.00 99.00 999.000000 99.000000 377.72
094327	6	Launch	375.60 -44.70 17.54 295.30 32.30 - 15.30 -14.399000 62.056500 7627.10
095218	6	Splashdown	1012.29 1.10 92.98 48.03 7.99 - 10.87 -14.354172 62.043487 389.94
094854	7	Launch	375.70 -44.80 9.35 296.60 31.40 - 14.90 -13.172200 62.045600 7626.10
095736	7	Splashdown	1011.34 -0.13 94.20 62.37 8.05 - 12.00 -13.070902 62.044629 421.77
095344	8	Launch	374.74 -11.73 1.72 999.00 999.00 99.00 999.000000 99.000000 99999.00
100308	8	Splashdown	1012.04 0.09 93.08 26.51 1.64 - 10.84 -11.956015 62.022029 716.27
095836	9	Launch	375.50 -45.10 9.92 300.00 30.90 - 14.60 -10.991200 61.999400 7628.50
100750	9	Splashdown	1012.36 2.73 59.33 327.45 2.89 - 10.94 -10.846945 61.980267 99999.00
102145	10	Launch	375.50 -43.10 63.15 284.30 41.80 - 15.50 -11.003800 59.994700 7628.50
103051	10	Splashdown	1014.17 4.64 57.69 999.00 999.00 99.00 999.000000 99.000000 99999.00
105154	11	Launch	359.70 -42.60 29.27 305.40 59.30 - 14.90 -14.874100 60.003100 7928.50
110118	11	Splashdown	1012.30 5.92 60.14 187.12 5.82 - 10.89 -14.709942 59.984937 99999.00
111209	12	Launch	344.00 -46.60 54.64 301.00 44.00 - 15.00 -14.999900 61.508300 8236.70

112153	12	Splashdown	1011.26	2.02	94.99	999.00	999.00	
			99.00	999.000000	99.000000	361.61		
113033	13	Launch	343.06	-13.93	1.41	999.00	999.00	
			99.00	999.000000	99.000000	8597.52		
113624	13	Splashdown	1011.17	-0.10	45.85	100.49	4.87	-
			0.17	-14.928718	62.977819	99999.00		
114706	14	Launch	344.10	-49.30	16.73	304.10	28.20	-
			13.50	-15.981600	64.267100	8234.20		
115602	14	Land	965.71	-3.97	50.17	188.78	0.24	-
			8.54	-15.867948	64.227958	846.03		
131957	15	Launch	328.90	-44.90	57.81	282.40	51.60	-
			14.70	-19.003600	60.002400	8542.90		
132956	15	Splashdown	1010.77	6.68	65.50	999.00	999.00	
			99.00	999.000000	99.000000	99999.00		

Flight:

B272

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevzorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

Report Created 15/03/2007
12:12:26

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

14/03/2007 15:55:15

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B272

Date: 26 Feb 2007

Instruments

- 1.
- 2.

Aircraft

- 1.

Satcom-H Calls

Nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Flight Manager's Data Processing Status

Flight No: B272
Flight Manager:AMW

Date of flight: 26/2/07

Mfd data must be backed up within a week.

If it can't be done by the Cloud Physics Operator in that time the **FM must back it up**

<u>On day of flight</u>		
Action	Link / Option	Date
Update Database & Note BBR Fit	Database	26/2/07
Create Fltcons & check BBR fit	Option 9	26/2/07
Transfer & process Data	Option 2	26/2/07
Ftp qldata to BADC	project_spaces/faam/quicklook	26/2/07
Check Rawdata	flight_plot	26/2/07
Raw data to BADC	Option 7	26/2/07
Copy & Convert Fltsumm file	Copy from optical to fltsumm directory Set def fltsumm run tarexec:convert_summ	26/2/07
Edit Fltsumm/ send to BADC	Option 10	26/2/07
Copy Flight logs to Seagate	Flight Logs	26/2/07
Download photos, clear camera & email Doug	To Flight Logs and Turb Probe Photos	26/2/07
Ftp CGPS.bin file to BADC	project_spaces/faam/javad_gps	-
Check MFDdata	flight_plot	26/2/07

<u>On day after flight</u>		
Action	Link / Option	Date
Ftp PSAP to FLOODS	Bnnn_psap_data	-
Merge PSAP into mfddata	wave .run mergepsap bnnn_mfda (b,c)	-
Record any MFD changes	edit mfddata:mfddata.txt	-
NETCDF to BADC	Option 4	26/2/07
Upload .nc from BADC	To USB stick (WS_FTP Pro)	26/2/07
Data quality check	Run Checkg on Linux pc	26/2/07
Ftp file to BADC	/incoming/faam/campaign-processed-core	26/2/07
Print out quality file	put in Faults Book	-
Backup raw data to optical then to firesafe	Option 6	26/2/07
Backup mfd if Cloud Physics Operator can't	MFD Backup Instructions.doc	26/2/07
Ftp mfd to BADC	Not yet set up	Watch this space
Video tapes to PI or cupboard	Video Tape Log	26/2/07
Complete & save this form	Data Processing Logs	26/2/07

1810: 1424

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B272:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Core Chemistry	No In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
Cloud Physics	Not operated on this flight

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	20 Mar 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1	10 Oct 2007	Doug Anderson	Added GFDex wx brief 26feb and Flight Manager Data Processing Status log
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Forward Facing Cameras
3 x Rearward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

Dr Ian A. Renfrew

Dr Ian A. Renfrew
Reader in Climate System Dynamics
School of Environmental Sciences
University of East Anglia
Norwich, NR4 7TJ, United Kingdom
Room: 2.33

Tel: +44 (0) 1603 592557
Fax: +44 (0) 1603 591327

E-mail: i.renfrew@uea.ac.uk

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r0	20 Mar 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Forward Facing Cameras
3 x Rearward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

Dr Ian A. Renfrew

Dr Ian A. Renfrew
Reader in Climate System Dynamics
School of Environmental Sciences
University of East Anglia
Norwich, NR4 7TJ, United Kingdom
Room: 2.33

Tel: +44 (0) 1603 592557
Fax: +44 (0) 1603 591327

E-mail: i.renfrew@uea.ac.uk

The second most beautiful polar low??

GFDex Weather & Sortie Brief

Monday 26th February

Mesoscale cyclone and
Targeted Observation mission

Outlook

- Monday 26th : Mesoscale cyclone
+Targeted flight; also **Sky TV!**
- Tuesday 27th : down day
- Wednesday 28th : down day

MSLP for T+24 DT 200702251200 VT 200702261200 ukmo nae main NWP
level 500 Geopotential Height for T+24 DT 200702251200 VT 200702261200 ukmo nae main NWP

MSLP for T+36 DT 200702250000 VT 200702261200 ukmo nae main NWP
level 500 Geopotential Height for T+36 DT 200702250000 VT 200702261200 ukmo nae main NWP

MSLP for T+0 DT 200702251200 VT 200702251200 ukmo nae main NWP
level 500 Geopotential Height for T+0 DT 200702251200 VT 200702251200 ukmo nae main NWP

MSLP for T+24 DT 200702251200 VT 200702261200 ukmo nae main NWP
level 500 Geopotential Height for T+24 DT 200702251200 VT 200702261200 ukmo nae main NWP

level -1 10m Wind for T+24 DT 200702251200 VT 200702261200 ukmo nae main NWP

level -1 Low Cloud for T+24 DT 200702251200 VT 200702261200 ukmo nae main NWP
level -1 Medium Cloud for T+24 DT 200702251200 VT 200702261200 ukmo nae main NWP
MSLP for T+24 DT 200702251200 VT 200702261200 ukmo nae main NWP

MSLP for T+24 DT 200702251200 VT 200702261200 ukmo nae main NWP

level 925 Temperature for T+24 DT 200702251200 VT 200702261200 ukmo nae main NWP

HIRLAM-T: Cloud cover: Low, mid and high clouds.

IT: Sun. 25. Feb. 2007 12Z

VT: Mon. 26.02.2007 12Z (+24 h)

HIRLAM-T: 3h precipitation, 10m wind and 2m temperature.

IT: Sun. 25. Feb. 2007 12Z

VT: **Mon. 26.02.2007 12Z (+24 h)**

HIRLAM-T: Sensible (colored) and latent (contours) heat flux at the surface.

IT: Sun. 25. Feb. 2007 12Z

VT: **Mon. 26.02.2007 12Z** (+24 h)

- **Aims**
- Map out 3D structure of mesoscale cyclone using a mixture of high-level and low-level legs
- High-level legs at 25-27 kft, straight and level, cutting through cyclone with cross.
- Low-level legs at 2000 ft and 5000 ft, straight and level, to sample wind, temperature, etc
- Dropsonde sampling every 30 nm (30-50 km) within cyclone
- Dropsonde release near Icelandic coast for topographic gravity waves
- Dropsonde releases evenly spaced around SAP for Targeted observation purposes

Mesoscale cyclone - GFDex Plan 44

- outbound
- high-level
- low-level
- return
- dropsonde leg

MSLP for T+24 DT 200702251200 VT 200702261200 ukmo nae main NWP
Level 500 Geopotential Height for T+24 DT 200702251200 VT 200702261200 ukmo nae main NWP

ECMWF-SAP based on TE-SVs (dry T42) and MSL

Valid time: 20070226, 12 UT (Targeting Time)

Shading: areas of 8, 4, 2, 1 x10⁶ km²

trajectory initialized from fc 20070225, 00 UT +36 h

Targ. time: 20070226, 12 UT / Verif. time: 20070228, 00 UT (opt: 36h)

ECMWF-SAP based on TE-SVs (dry T42) and MSL

Valid time: 20070226, 12 UT (Targeting Time)

Shading: areas of 8, 4, 2, 1 x10⁶ km²

trajectory initialized from fc 20070224, 12 UT +48 h

Targ. time: 20070226, 12 UT / Verif. time: 20070228, 12 UT (opt: 48h)

UKMO-SAP based on MOGREPS15-initialised ETKF summary map (colour)
MOGREPS control fc MSLP (black solid contour)

Shading: areas of 8, 4, 2, 1 x 10⁶ km²
Trajectory initialised from fc 20070225, 0 +36h (Lead time)
Targ. time: 20070226, 12UT / Verif. time: 20070228, 0UT (opt:36)

UKMO-SAP based on MOGREPS15-initialised ETKF summary map (colour)

MOGREPS control fc MSLP (black solid contour)

Maximum ETKF signal variance: 0.58

Trajectory initialised from fc 20070225, 0 +36h (Lead time)

Targ. time: 20070226, 12UT / Verif. time: 20070228, 0UT (opt:36)

Outlook

- Monday: Mesoscale cyclone + Targeted flight
- Tuesday: down day
- Wednesday: down day
- Thursday:

MSLP for T+48 DT 200702250000 VT 200702270000 ukmo global main NWP
level 500 Geopotential Height for T+48 DT 200702250000 VT 200702270000 ukmo global main NWP

MSLP for T+60 DT 200702250000 VT 200702271200 ukmo global main NWP
level 500 Geopotential Height for T+60 DT 200702250000 VT 200702271200 ukmo global main NWP

Sunday 25 February 2007 00UTC ECMWF Forecast t+84 VT: Wednesday 28 February 2007 12UTC Surface: mean sea level pressure

Sunday 25 February 2007 00UTC ECMWF Forecast t+96 VT: Thursday 1 March 2007 00UTC Surface: mean sea level pressure

Sunday 25 February 2007 00UTC ECMWF Forecast t+102 VT: Thursday 1 March 2007 06UTC Surface: mean sea level pressure

Sunday 25 February 2007 00UTC ECMWF Forecast t+108 VT: Thursday 1 March 2007 12UTC Surface: mean sea level pressure

Sunday 25 February 2007 00UTC ECMWF Forecast t+120 VT: Friday 2 March 2007 00UTC Surface: mean sea level pressure

Outlook

- Monday 26th : Mesoscale cyclone
+Targeted flight; also **Sky TV!**
- Tuesday 27th : down day
- Wednesday 28th : down day

Outlook

- Thursday 1st: Lee cyclogenesis?
 - UKMO FC SE Greenland, EC near Iceland
- or Barrier wind?

- Friday 2nd : Westerly Tip Jet event?
 - UKMO FC
 - ECMWF FC?
- Or Barrier wind?

Daily weather summary 26 February 2007

<p>Large scale situation today:</p>	<p>The low off Newfoundland has filled to 977hPa with a second low passing it from the southwest. These low pressure systems merge during the day with a trough extending east across the Atlantic. Two new low pressure centres are predicted to form in this trough by the end of the day. The low to the northwest of Iceland is quasi-stationary. The cloud around this system is still well defined. The weather between Iceland and Greenland is dominated by the high pressure system over Greenland. The cyclone over the UK has moved off towards Denmark.</p> <p>The trough extending to the east, south-southeast of Iceland in the UKMO global was predicted to form a closed low in the forecast from the day before.</p>
<p>Features of interest:</p>	<p>The models have suggested that the trough to the south-southeast of Iceland will give rise to a small mesoscale cyclone. There is little else of interest in the area.</p> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 10px;"> <p style="text-align: center;">Analysis chart valid 00 UTC Mon 26 FEB 2007</p> </div>
<p>Action:</p>	<p>The plan is to investigate the mesoscale cyclone to the south of Iceland along with an SAP flight.</p>
<p>Outlook for the next 24-48 hours:</p>	<p>The North Atlantic is dominated by the two low pressure systems which deepen to 966hPa and travel across towards the UK. The high pressure system over Greenland breaks up and the low to the northeast of Iceland moves away.</p>
<p>Outlook for the next 48-96 hours:</p>	<p>The first low moving towards the UK slows over Scotland before continuing on towards Scandinavia. The second low dissipates while a new centre forms in its northern trough, in the lee of the Greenland tip. A possible barrier flow begins to form to the north of Iceland on the 1st March, 2007.</p>

Flight B272 12:49:44
 Heading 185 deg Speed 210 knots Height 2.0kft Press 940mb
 Lat 60°36.0'N Long 15°0.0'W Wind 7 ms-1/ 226 deg
 Temp -0.34C Dewpoint -2.46C
 From 12:14:05 to now

Wind Speed

Flight B272 12:51:02
 Heading 258 deg Speed 211 knots Height 2.1kft Press 937mb
 Lat 60°36.0'N Long 15°6.0'W Wind 5 ms-1/ 229 deg
 Temp 0.2C Dewpoint -3.46C
 From 12:14:05 to now

Wind Component

Flight B272 12:53:14
 Heading 250 deg Speed 256 knots Height 5.0kft Press 841mb
 Lat 60°30.0'N Long 15°24.0'W Wind 6 ms-1/ 250 deg
 Temp -6.93C Dewpoint -7.45C
 From 12:21:46 to now

U component

Flight B272 12:51:56
 Heading 262 deg Speed 241 knots Height 3.8kft Press 880mb
 Lat 60°36.0'N Long 15°12.0'W Wind 2 ms-1/ 96 deg
 Temp -4.09C Dewpoint -4.14C
 From 12:21:46 to now

V component

Flight B272 12:55:05
 Heading 254 deg Speed 247 knots Height 5.0kft Press 842mb
 Lat 60°30.0'N Long 15°36.0'W Wind 6 ms-1/ 275 deg
 Temp -6.66C Dewpoint -7.34C
 From 12:21:46 to now

Flight B272 12:56:33
 Heading 253 deg Speed 239 knots Height 4.7kft Press 851mb
 Lat 60°30.0'N Long 15°48.0'W Wind 7 ms-1/ 262 deg
 Temp -6.0C Dewpoint -6.75C
 From 12:21:46 to now

Temperature

Flight B272 12:58:08
 Heading 252 deg Speed 261 knots Height 4.0kft Press 872mb
 Lat 60°24.0'N Long 16°0.0'W Wind 6 ms-1/ 261 deg
 Temp -4.03C Dewpoint -6.09C
 From 12:21:46 to now

Temperature and Dew Point Temperature

Flight B272 13:03:27
 Heading 254 deg Speed 262 knots Height 4.0kft Press 872mb
 Lat 60°18.0'N Long 16°42.0'W Wind 5 ms-1/ 295 deg
 Temp -4.09C Dewpoint -5.49C
 From 12:21:46 to now

Theta thetae

Flight B272 13:23:32
 Heading 14 deg Speed 321 knots Height 28.0kft Press 329mb
 Lat 60°6.0'N Long 19°6.0'W Wind 46 ms-1/ 285 deg
 Temp -44.98C Dewpoint -49.63C
 From 12:21:46 to now

Geopht

